

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

UNIT-I

The business system - objectives of the business - setting up and balancing the objectives mission - vision - goals strategic analysis of functional areas production - marketing - human resources - finance - analyzing corporate capabilities.

The business system

Definition

According to well-known professors William Pride, Robert Hughes, and Jack Kapoor, business is 'the organized effort of individuals to produce and sell, for a profit, the goods and services that satisfy society's needs.' A business, then, is an organization which seeks to make a profit through individuals working toward common goals. The goals of the business will vary based on the type of business and the business strategy being used. Regardless of the preferred strategy, businesses must provide a service, product, or good that meets a need of society in some way.

Characteristics of Business

There are three key characteristics that must be met to have a business.

First, businesses must be the result of individuals working together in an organized way.

Second, businesses must satisfy a societal need.

Third, businesses must seek to make a profit.

As Pride, Hughes and Kapoor note, businesses are comprised of individuals working together in an organized way in order to be successful. Businesses are organized around the resources needed to be successful, as well as the type of business that is being operated. Some businesses may be organized in a way that requires constant cooperation and communication with other employees. Other businesses may not require as much contact with other employees but may instead rely on automated workflows. They must decide the best way to be organized based on their individual goals.

Businesses must also satisfy a need for society. For example, a grocery store satisfies the need to be able to purchase food for ourselves and our families.

Another example of satisfying a societal need is a gas station that provides needed fuel for most cars to operate.

Businesses must carefully consider what need they are meeting for society in order to strategically plan for success. For example, society may have a limited interest in

purchasing a personal hovercraft for travel. Travel needs are currently met in other ways, so a business focused solely on personal hovercraft may struggle more than the gas station at meeting a definite need.

Objectives of Business

The objectives of a business can be classified into two main categories, which are

Economic objectives

Social objectives

Economic Objectives of Business

We learned in the previous topic that business is an [economic activity](#). Hence, its purpose is to show economic results. Let's understand the economic objectives of the business. They are as follows:

1] Profit Earning

Business is a set of activities undertaken with the prospect of sale for the purpose of earning a profit. Profit is the extra income over the expenses. The main objective of any business is to earn a profit. Just as a plant cannot survive without [water](#), similarly a business cannot sustain without profit.

Profit is necessary for growing and expanding [business activities](#). Profit guarantee a consistent stream of capital for the modernization and augmentation of business activities in the future. Profits likewise show the scale of stability, efficiency, and advancement of the [business organization](#).

2] Market Share / Creation of Customers

In the words of Drucker, "There is only one valid definition of business purpose; to create a customer." Profits are not generated out of thin air. They are the result of the hard work of the businessman to satisfy the needs of the customers.

In the long run, the survival of the business completely depends upon the [market](#) share captured by the business. The creation of good and satisfaction of the needs of the customer is a crucial purpose of the business. So to generate profit and demand, the business must supply premium quality and give value for [money](#) products.

3] Innovation & Utilization of Resources

Innovation normally means to change processes or creating more effective processes, products and ideas. Nowadays, business is ever-changing and dynamic. To keep up with the growing competition a businessman has to introduce efficient design, latest trends, upgraded machinery, new techniques, etc.

Large corporations invest a humongous amount of capital in their Research & Development department to boost innovation. Whereas, on the parallel lines, utilization of resources is a proper use of workforce, raw material, capital and technology used in the business. A business has limited resources and that's why its main objective is to put these [resources](#) to correct divisions.

4] Increasing Productivity

Productivity is a scale to measure the efficiency of the business activity. It is usually the last objective but just as important because productivity is measured by the output given by the activities. It is the end result of any business activity. Each business must go for more prominent productivity – to guarantee its survival and development. This goal can be accomplished by decreasing wastages and making proficient utilization of machines and supplies, HR, cash and so forth.

Social Objectives of Business

According to Dayton Hudson “The business of business is serving society, not just making money.” Business is one of the pillars on which the society stands. Therefore, it is a part of the society. In fact, it cannot thrive without the resources from the society. The business earns its income from the sale of products and services to the society. It is mandatory on the part of the business to take care of the social factors. The necessary social objectives of a business are as follows:

1] Providing Goods & Services at Reasonable Prices

Business exists in the first place to satisfy the needs of the society. It's the first and major social objective of the business. [Products](#) and services ought to be of better quality and these ought to be provided at sensible costs. It is additionally the social commitment of business to keep away from misbehaviors like boarding, Black promoting and manipulative advertising.

2] Employment Generation

One of the major problem today's generation facing is unemployment. Business generates employment. Therefore, it is the social objective of a business to give chances to beneficial employment to individuals of the society. In a nation like India, unemployment has turned into a critical issue.

3] Fair Remuneration to Employees

The business does not run on its own but the people are responsible for the success and failure of the business. The people on the inside of the business are more valuable i.e. employees. They are an asset of the business and make a ground-breaking contribution to the business. They must be given reasonable pay for their work.

Notwithstanding wages and salary, a significant piece of profits ought to be distributed among them in acknowledgment of their commitments. Such sharing of benefits will expand the inspiration and proficiency of employees.

4] Community Service

Business must give back something to the society. As a result, the Library, dispensary, educational foundations and so on which a business can make and help in the advancement of society are created. Business enterprises can build schools, colleges, libraries, hospitals, sports bodies and research institutions. They can help non-government organizations (NGOs) like CRY, Help Age, and others which render services to weaker sections of society.

Mission Statement

The first component of the strategic management process is crafting the organization's mission statement, which provides the framework or context within which strategies are formulated. A mission statement has four main components: a statement of the *raison d'être* of a company or organization—its reason for existence—which is normally

referred to as the mission; a statement of some desired future state, usually referred to as the vision; a statement of the key values that the organization is committed to; and a statement of major goals.

Mission of an organization is the purpose for which the organization is. Mission is again a single statement, and carries the statement in verb. Mission in one way is the road to achieve the vision. For example, for a luxury products company, the vision could be 'To be among most admired luxury brands in the world' and mission could be 'To add style to the lives'

A good mission statement will be:

Clear and Crisp: While there are different views, we strongly recommend that mission should only provide what, and not 'how and when'. We would prefer the mission of 'Making People meet their career' to 'making people meet their career through effective career counseling and education'. A mission statement without 'how

& when' element leaves a creative space with the organization to enable them take-up wider strategic choices.

Have to have a very visible linkage to the business goals and strategy: For example, you cannot have a mission (for a home furnishing company) of 'Bringing Style to People's lives' while your strategy asks for mass product and selling. It's better that either you start selling high-end products to high value customers, OR change your mission statement to 'Help people build homes'.

Should not be same as the mission of a competing organization. It should touch upon how its purpose is unique.

The Mission A company's mission describes what the company does. For example, the mission of Kodak is to provide —customers with the solutions they need to capture, store, process, output, and communicate images—anywhere, anytime. || An important first step in the process of formulating a mission is to arrive at a definition of the organization's business. Essentially, the definition answers these questions: —What is our business? What will it be? What should it be?||⁷ There are three questions that guide the formulation of the mission. To answer the question, —What is our business?|| a company should define its business in terms of three dimensions: who is being satisfied (what customer groups); what is being satisfied (what customer needs); and how customers' needs are being satisfied (by what skills, knowledge, or distinctive competencies).

Vision

The vision of a company lays out some desired future state; it articulates, often in bold terms, what the company would like to achieve. Nokia, the world's largest manufacturer of mobile (wireless) phones, has been operating with a very simple but powerful vision for some time: —If it can go mobile, it will!|| This vision implied that not only would voice technology go mobile but also a host of other services based on data, such as imaging and Internet browsing. This vision led Nokia to become a leader in developing mobile handsets that not only can be used for voice communication but also take pictures, browse the Internet, play games, and manipulate personal and corporate information.

Mission and Objectives

The mission statement describes the company's business vision, including the unchanging values and purpose of the firm and forward looking visionary goals that guide the pursuit of future opportunities. Guided by the business vision, the firm's leaders can define measurable financial and strategic objectives. Financial objectives involve measures such as sales targets and earnings growth. Strategic objectives are related to the firm's business position, and may include measures such as market share and reputation.

Functional Areas of Business Strategy

are to be integrated into the business policy process. They are

1. Production
2. Marketing
3. Finance
4. Personal

5. R & D

6. Legal

Production:

The production department will address the questions relating to size of production quality of the product to consumer expectation.

Marketing:

The marketing department will highlight the capabilities & limitations of the product promotion. Physical distribution & personal etc.

Finance:

The finance department is responsible for both short term & long-term financiers at competitive costs return on investments.

Research & Development:

R&D is nerves system of the organization. It plays vital role in translation vision in to reality.

Legal:

The legal department should answer the questions relating to patent rights & liabilities.

Personal:

Personal is most crucial component of the organization. It is involved in all functional areas. It is concerned with selecting the best people. Satisfying them through motivation & training

Strategy

Strategy is a tactical course of action which is designed to achieve long term objectives. It is an art and science of planning and marshalling resources for their most efficient and effective use in a changing environment.

Strategy of a business enterprise consists of what management decides about the future direction and scope of the business. It entails managerial choice among alternative action programmes, competitive moves and different business approaches to achieve enterprise objectives.

Definition of Strategy

As per Glueck,

Strategy is unified, comprehensive and integrated plan relating the strategic advantages of the firm to the challenges of the environment. It is designed to ensure that the basic objectives of the enterprise are achieved.

As per Alfred D. Chandler,

Strategy is “The determination of basic long-term goals and objectives of an enterprise and the adoption of the courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying out these goals.”

Features of Strategy

Top management responsibility

Allocation of large amount of resources

Impact on long term prosperity of the firm

Future oriented

Multi-functional or multi-business consequences

Consideration of factors in the external environment

Levels of Strategy

Corporate-level Strategy

At this level, strategic decisions relate to organization-wide policies and are taken care by top-level management (BOD) with a vision of determining ‘Where the company wants to be?’ It has two main aspects- Formulation of Strategy (strategic planning) and Strategy Implementation.

The nature of strategy at this level tend to be value-oriented, conceptual and than other levels. There is also greater risk, cost and profit potential as well as greater need of flexibility associated with this level.

Major financial policy decisions involving acquisition, diversification and structural redesigning belong to this level.

Business-Level Strategy

Business-level strategy is more likely related to a unit within the whole. It is concerned with competition in a market. The concerns are about what products or services should be developed and offered to which markets in order to meet customer needs and organizational objectives.

At this level, multifunctional strategies developed at corporate level are formulated and implemented for specific product market in which the business operates. Thus, managers at this level translate general directions and intent into concrete functional objectives.

Decisions at this level include policies involving new product development, marketing mix, research & development, personnel, etc.

Functional/Operational-Level Strategy

Functional strategy involves decision-making with respect to specific functional areas- production, marketing, personnel, finance etc.

While corporate and business level strategies are concerned with “Doing the right things”, functional strategies stress on “Doing things right”.

Operating level strategy is concerned with strategic approaches for managing frontline operating units(like plants, sales, etc) and for handling day to day tasks of strategic significance(like advertising campaign, purchasing materials, inventory control, maintenance, etc.).

Thus, functional level strategic management is the management of relatively narrow areas of activity, which are of vital, pervasive or continuing importance to the total organization.

Analyzing corporate capabilities.

Environmental Scan

The environmental scan includes the following components:

Analysis of the firm (Internal environment)

Analysis of the firm's industry (micro or task environment)

Analysis of the External macro environment (PEST analysis)

The internal analysis can identify the firm's strengths and weaknesses and the external analysis reveals opportunities and threats. A profile of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats is generated by means of a SWOT analysis

An industry analysis can be performed using a framework developed by Michael Porter known as Porter's five forces. This framework evaluates entry barriers, suppliers, customers, substitute products, and industry rivalry.

(a) The environment

The organization exists in the context of a complex commercial, economic, political, technological, cultural, and social world. This environment changes and is more complex for some organizations than for others. Since strategy is concerned with the position a business takes in relation to its environment, an understanding of the environment's effects on a business is of central importance to strategic analysis. The historical and environmental effects on the business must be considered, as well as the present effects and the expected changes in environmental variables. This is a major task because the range of environmental variables is so great. Many of those variables will give rise to opportunities of some sort, and many will exert threats upon the firm. The two main problems that have to be faced are, first, to distil out of this complexity a view of the main or overall environmental impacts for the purpose of strategic choice; and second, the fact that the range of variables is likely to be so great that it may not be possible or realistic to identify and analyse each one.

(b) The resources of the organization

Just as there are outside influences on the firm and its choice of strategies, so there are internal influences. One way of thinking about the strategic capability of an organization is to consider its strengths and weaknesses (what it is good or not so good at doing, or where it is at a competitive advantage or disadvantage, for example). These strengths and weaknesses may be identified by considering the resource areas of a business such as its physical plant, its management, its financial structure, and its products. Again, the aim is to form a view of the internal influences -- and constraints -- on strategic choice.

c) Strategy Formulation

Strategy Formulation is the development of long-range plans for the effective management of environmental opportunities and threats, in light of corporate strengths & weakness. It includes defining the corporate mission, specifying achievable objectives, developing strategy & setting policy guidelines.

d) Strategy Implementation

It is the process by which strategy & policies are put into actions through the development of programs, budgets & procedures. This process might involve changes

within the overall culture, structure and/or management system of the entire organization.

i) Programs:

It is a statement of the activities or steps needed to accomplish a single-use plan. It makes the strategy action oriented. It may involve restructuring the corporation, changing the company's internal culture or beginning a new research effort.

ii) Budgets:

A budget is a statement of a program in terms of dollars. Used in planning & control, a budget lists the detailed cost of each program. The budget thus not only serves as a detailed plan of the new strategy in action, but also specifies through proforma financial statements the expected impact on the firm's financial future

iii) Procedures:

Procedures, sometimes termed Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) are a system of sequential steps or techniques that describe in detail how a particular task or job is to be done. They typically detail the various activities that must be carried out in order to complete

e) Evaluation & Control

After the strategy is implemented it is vital to continually measure and evaluate progress so that changes can be made if needed to keep the overall plan on track. This is known as the control phase of the strategic planning process. While it may be necessary to develop systems to allow for monitoring progress, it is well worth the effort. This is also where performance standards should be set so that performance may be measured and leadership can make adjustments as needed to ensure success.

Evaluation and control consists of the following steps:

Define parameters to be measured

Define target values for those parameters

Perform measurements

Compare measured results to the pre-defined standard

Make necessary changes

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

UNIT 2

Mintzberg has identified the 5 P's of strategy. Strategy could be a plan, a pattern, a position, a ploy, or a perspective.

A plan, a "how do I get there"

A pattern, in consistent actions over time

A position that is, it reflects the decision of the firm to offer particular products or services in particular markets.

A ploy, a maneuver intended to outwit a competitor

A perspective that is, a vision and direction, a view of what the company or organization is to become.

Nature and Scope of Strategy

Strategic management is basically needed for every organization and it offers several benefits.

1. Universal

Strategy refers to a complex web of thoughts, ideas, insights, experiences, goals, expertise, memories, perceptions, and expectations that provides general guidance for specific actions in pursuit of particular ends. Nations have, in the management of their national policies, found it necessary to evolve strategies that adjust and correlate political, economic, technological, and psychological factors, along with military elements. Be it management of national polices, international relations, or even of a game on the playfield, it provides us with the preferred path that we should take for the journey that we actually make.

2. Keeping pace with changing environment

The present day environment is so dynamic and fast changing thus making it very difficult for any modern business enterprise to operate. Because of uncertainties, threats and constraints, the business corporation are under great pressure and are trying to find out the ways and means for their healthy survival. Under such circumstances, the only last resort is to make the best use of strategic management which can help the corporate management to explore the possible opportunities and at the same time to achieve an optimum level of efficiency by minimizing the expected threats.

3. Minimizes competitive disadvantage

It minimizes competitive disadvantage and adds up to competitive advantage. For example, a company like Hindustan Lever Ltd., realized that merely by merging with companies like Lakme, Milk food, Ponds, Brooke bond, Lipton etc which make fast moving consumer goods alone will not make it market leader but venturing into retailing will help it reap heavy profits. Then emerged its retail giant "Margin Free" which is the market leader in states like Kerala. Similarly, the R.P. Goenka Group and the Murugappa group realized that mere takeovers do not help and there is a need to reposition their products and reengineer their brands. The strategy worked.

4. Clear sense of strategic vision and sharper focus on goals and objectives

Every firm competing in an industry has a strategy, because strategy refers to how a given objective will be achieved. 'Strategy' defines what it is we want to achieve and charts our course in the market place; it is the basis for the establishment of a business firm; and it is a basic requirement for a firm to survive and to sustain itself in today's changing environment by providing vision and encouraging to define mission.

5. Motivating employees

One should note that the labor efficiency and loyalty towards management can be expected only in an organization that operates under strategic management. Every guidance as to what to do, when and how to do and by whom etc, is given to every employee. This makes them more confident and free to perform their tasks without any hesitation. Labor efficiency and their loyalty which results into industrial peace and good returns are the results of broad-based policies adopted by the strategic management

6. Strengthening Decision-Making

Under strategic management, the first step to be taken is to identify the objectives of the business concern. Hence a corporation organized under the basic principles of strategic management will find a smooth sailing due to effective decision-making. This points out the need for strategic management.

7. Efficient and effective way of implementing actions for results

Strategy provides a clear understanding of purpose, objectives and standards of performance to employees at all levels and in all functional areas. Thereby it makes implementation very smooth allowing for maximum harmony and synchrony. As a result, the expected results are obtained more efficiently and economically.

8. Improved understanding of internal and external environments of business

Strategy formulation requires continuous observation and understanding of environmental variables and classifying them as opportunities and threats. It also involves knowing whether the threats are serious or casual and opportunities are worthy or marginal. As such strategy provides for a better understanding of environment.

CORPORATE AND STRATEGIC PLANNING

Strategic planning is the establishment of viable connections among long-term objectives, resources and environmental conditions of an organization by using certain methods and activities.

Strategic planning is an organizational management activity that is used to set priorities, focus energy and resources, strengthen operations, ensure that employees and other stakeholders are working toward common goals, establish agreement around intended outcomes/results, and assess and adjust the organization's direction in response to a changing environment. It is a disciplined effort that produces fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, who it serves, what it does, and why it does it, with a focus on the future. Effective strategic planning articulates not only where an organization is

going and the actions needed to make progress, but also how it will know if it is successful.

Steps of the strategic planning process

Definition of organizational mission	Definition of organizational goals	Analysis of external Environment	Identification of internal organizational strengths and weaknesses	Research and analysis of strategic alternatives
Strategy evaluation	Realization control of strategic plans		Strategy implementation	Strategy selection

Strategic Planning Process

Strategic Planning Approach

Formulation of strategy

1. Conduct an environmental scan. Review your organization's strengths and weaknesses. Reflect on the community and broader environment in which your organization operates to identify the opportunities and threats that it faces. Determine the community's assets and needs, specifically those of current/potential populations that you'll try to reach.

2. Identify key issues, questions, and choices to be addressed. Specify "strategic issues" that your organization should address and set priorities in terms of time or importance. Strategic issues emerge from the data and environmental scan.

3. Define or review the organization's values, community vision, and mission. Reach consensus on why the organization exists, what goals or outcomes it seeks to achieve, what it stands for, and whom it serves. Begin your strategic planning by agreeing on the following:

Strategic planning process

Figure 2

Strategic planning process

Organizational core values or operating principles – those beliefs/principles that guide the organization - these are shared, strongly held, and not easily changed. Community Vision – the vision for your community - an image of what it would be like if your values were shared and practiced by everyone. Mission – the stated purpose for your organization's existence; the contribution it promises to make to help accomplish the community vision.

4. Transform the vision and mission into a series of key goals for your organization

5. Agree upon key strategies to address strategic issues and reach goals. The emphasis should be on broad strategies, including current/new collaborative approaches that are related to specific goal(s). The process requires that you look at where the organization is now, where its vision and goals indicate it wants to be, and identify strategies to get there. Specific criteria for evaluating and choosing among strategies should be agreed upon, such as the following:

- Value and Appropriateness – Is the strategy consistent with your organization's mission, values, operating principles, and agreed-upon goals?
- Feasibility – Is the strategy practical given current personnel, financial resources and capacity?
- Acceptability – Is the strategy acceptable to your stakeholders?
- Cost-benefit – Is the strategy likely to lead to benefits that justify time, costs and other resources?

6. Create an annual action plan that addresses goals and specifies objectives/work plan. Once long-term elements of your strategic plan have been developed, create a specific work plan for implementation. Its strategies should reflect current organizational/environmental conditions. Objectives should be measurable and time-based. Under these or other agreed upon criteria, strategies can be evaluated, prioritized and chosen.

7. Finalize a written strategic plan that summarizes your decisions. Be sure to include the outputs of each major step.

8. Build in procedures for monitoring and modifying strategies. Monitor the progress towards goals, objectives and strategies and revise your plan based on progress made, obstacles encountered and the changing environment. Acknowledge and take advantage of unexpected changes, such as more sympathetic elected/appointed officials, economic improvements, and changes in funder priorities or the priority population.

Project Life Cycle /Industry Life Cycle

Industry lifecycle comprises four stages including fragmentation, growth, maturity and decline. An understanding of the industry lifecycle can help competing companies survive during periods of transition. Several variations of the lifecycle model have been developed to address the development and transition of products, market and industry. The models are similar but the number of stages and names of each may differ. Major models include those developed by Fox (1973), Wasson (1974), Anderson & Zeithaml (1984), and Hill & Jones (1998).

a) Fragmentation Stage

Fragmentation is the first stage of the new industry. This is the stage when the new industry develops the business. At this stage, the new industry normally arises when an entrepreneur overcomes the twin problems of [innovation](#) and invention, and works out how to bring the new products or services into the market. For example, air travel services of major [airlines](#) in Europe were sold to the target market at a high price. Therefore, the majority of airlines' customers in Europe were those people with high incomes who could afford premium prices for faster travel.

In 1985, [Ryanair](#) made a huge change in the European airline industry. [Ryanair](#) was the first airline to engage low-cost airlines in Europe. At that time, [Ryanair's](#) services were perceived as the innovation of the [European airline industry](#). [Ryanair](#) tickets are half the price of [British Airways](#). Some of its sales promotions were very low. This made people think that air travel was not just made for the rich, but everybody. [Ryanair](#) overcame the twin problems of innovation and invention in the airline industry by inventing air travel services that could serve passengers with tight budgets and those who just wanted to reach their destination without breaking their bank savings. [Ryanair](#) achieved this goal by eliminating unnecessary services offered by traditional airlines. It does not offer free meals, uses paper-free air tickets, gets rid of mile collecting scheme, utilises secondary airports, and offers frequent flights. These techniques help [Ryanair](#) save time and costs spent in airline business operation.

b) Shake-out

Shake-out is the second stage of the [industry lifecycle](#). It is the stage at which a new industry emerges. During the shake-out stage, competitors start to realise business opportunities in the emerging industry. The value of the industry also quickly rises. For example, many people die and suffer because of cigarettes every year. Thus, the UK government decided to launch a campaign to encourage people to quit smoking. [Nicorette](#), one of the leading companies is producing several nicotine products to help people quit smoking. Some of its well-known products include [Nicorette](#) patches, [Nicolette](#) gums and [Nicorette](#) lozenges.

Smokers began to see an easy way to quit smoking. The new industry started to attract brand recognition and brand awareness among its target market during the shake-out stage. Nicorette's products began to gain popularity among those who wanted to quit smoking or those who wanted to reduce their daily cigarette consumption.

During this period, another company realised the opportunity in this market and decided to enter it by launching nicotine product ranges, including Nic Lite gum and patches. It recently went beyond UK boarder after the UK government introduced non-smoking policy in public places, including pubs and nightclubs. This business threat created a new business opportunity in the industry for Nic Lite to launch a new nicotine-related product called Nic Time. Nic Time is a whole new way for smokers to "get a cigarette" – an eight-ounce bottle contains a lemon-flavoured drink laced with nicotine, the same amount of nicotine

as two cigarettes. Nic Lite was first available at Los Angeles airports for smokers who got uneasy on flights, but now the nicotine soft drinks are available in some convenience stores.

c) Maturity

Maturity is the third stage in the industry lifecycle. Maturity is a stage at which the efficiencies of the dominant business model give these organisations competitive advantage over competition. The competition in the industry is rather aggressive because there are many competitors and product substitutes. Price, competition, and cooperation take on a complex form. Some companies may shift some of the production overseas in order to gain competitive advantage.

For example, [Toyota](#) is one of the world's leading multinational companies, selling automobiles to customers worldwide. The export and import taxes mean that its cars lose competitiveness to the local competitors, especially in the European [automobile industry](#). As a result, [Toyota](#) decided to open a factory in the UK in order to produce cars and sell them to customers in the European market.

The haute couture fashion industry is another good example. There are many western-branded fashion labels that manufacture their products overseas by cooperating with overseas partners, or they could seek foreign suppliers who specialise in particular materials or items. For instance, [Nike](#) has factories in China and Thailand as both countries have cheap labour costs and cheap, quality materials, particularly rubber and fabric. However, their overseas partners are not allowed to sell shoes produced for [Adidas](#) and [Nike](#). The items have to be shipped back to the US, and then will be exported to countries worldwide, including China and Thailand.

d) Decline

Decline is the final stage of the industry lifecycle. Decline is a stage during which a war of slow destruction between businesses may develop and those with heavy bureaucracies may fail. In addition, the demand in the market may be fully satisfied or suppliers may be running out.

In the stage of decline, some companies may leave the industry if there is no demand for the products or services they provide, or they may develop new products or services that meet the demand in the market. In such cases, this will create a new industry.

For example, at the beginning of the communication industry, pagers were used as the main communication method among people working in the same organisation, such as doctors and nurses. Then, the cutting edge of the communication industry emerged in the form of the mobile phone. The communication process of pagers could not be accomplished without telephones. To send a message to another pager, the user had to phone the call-centre staff who would type and send the message to another pager. On the other hand, people who use mobile phones can make a phone-call and send messages to other mobiles without going through call-centre staff.

CORPORATE PORTFOLIO ANALYSIS

When the company is in more than one business, it can select more than one strategic alternative depending upon demand of the situation prevailing in the different portfolios. It is necessary to analyze the position of different business of the business house which is done by corporate portfolio analysis.

Portfolio analysis is an analytical tool which views a corporation as a basket or portfolio of products or business units to be managed for the best possible returns. When an organization has a number of products in its portfolio, it is quite likely that they will be in different stages of development. Some will be relatively new and some much older. Many organizations will not wish to risk having all their products at the same stage of development. It is useful to have some products with limited growth but producing profits steadily, and some products with real growth potential but may still be in the introductory stage. Indeed, the products that are earning steadily may be used to fund the development of those that will provide the growth and profits in the future.

So the key strategy is to produce a balanced portfolio of products, some with low risk but dull growth and some with high risk but great potential for growth and profits. This is what we call as portfolio analysis.

The aim of portfolio analysis is

- 1) to analyze its current business portfolio and decide which businesses should receive more or less investment
- 2) to develop growth strategies, for adding new businesses to the portfolio
- 3) to decide which business should not longer be retained

This analysis can be done by any of the following technologies –

- A) BCG matrix
- B) GE nine cell matrix

A) BCG MATRIX – the bcg matrix was developed by Boston Consulting group in 1970s. it is also called as the growth share matrix. This is the most popular and simplest matrix to describe the corporation's portfolio of businesses or products.

The BCG matrix helps to determine priorities in a product portfolio. Its basic purpose is to invest where there is growth from which the firm can benefit, and divest those businesses that have low market share and low growth prospects.

Each of the products or business units is plotted on a two dimensional matrix consisting of

- a) Relative market share – is the ratio of the market share of the concerned product or business unit in the industry divided by the share of the market leader
- b) Market growth rate – is the percentage of market growth, by which sales of a particular product or business unit has increased

Analysis of the BCG matrix – the matrix reflects the contribution of the products or business units to its cash flow. Based on this analysis, the products or business units are classified as –

- i) Stars
- ii) Cash cows
- iii) Question marks
- iv) Dogs

i) Stars – high growth, high market share

Stars are products that enjoy a relatively high market share in a strongly growing market. They are potentially profitable and may grow further to become an important product or category for the company. The firm should focus on and invest in these products or business units. The general features of stars are -

High growth rate means they need heavy investment

High market share means they have economies of scale and generate large amount of cash But they need more cash than they generate The high growth rate will mean that they will need heavy investment and will therefore be cash users. Overall, the general strategy is to take cash from the cash cows to fund stars. Cash may also be invested selectively in some problem children (question marks) to turn them into stars. The other problem children may be milked or even sold to provide funds elsewhere.

Over the time, all growth may slow down and the stars may eventually become cash cows. If they cannot hold market share, they may even become dogs.

ii) Cash Cows – Low growth, high market share

These are the product areas that have high relative market shares but exist in low-growth markets. The business is mature and it is assumed that lower levels of investment will be required. On this basis, it is therefore likely that they will be able to generate both cash and profits. Such profits could then be transferred to support the stars. The general features of cash cows are –

They generate both cash and profits

The business is mature and needs lower levels of investment

Profits are transferred to support stars/question marks

The danger is that cash cows may become under-supported and begin to lose their market. Although the market is no longer growing, the cash cows may have a relatively high market share and bring in healthy profits. No efforts or investments are necessary to maintain the status quo. Cash cows may however ultimately become dogs if they lose the market share.

iii) Question Marks – high growth, low market share

Question marks are also called problem children or wild cats. These are products with low relative market shares in high growth markets. The high market growth means that considerable investment may still be required and the low market share will mean that such products will have difficulty in generating substantial cash. These businesses are called question marks because the organization must decide whether to strengthen them or to sell them.

The general features of question marks are –

Their cash needs are high

But their cash generation is low

Organization must decide whether to strengthen them or sell them. Although their market share is relatively small, the market for question marks is growing rapidly. Investments to create growth may yield big results in the future, though this is far from certain. Further investigation into how and where to invest is advised.

iv) Dogs – Low growth, low market share

These are products that have low market shares in low growth businesses. These products will need low investment but they are unlikely to be major profit earners. In practice, they may actually absorb cash required to hold their position. They are often regarded as unattractive for the long term and recommended for disposal. The general features of dogs are –

They are not profit earners

They absorb cash

They are unattractive and are often recommended for disposal.

Turnaround can be one of the strategies to pursue because many dogs have bounced back and become viable and profitable after asset and cost reduction. The suggested strategy is to drop or divest the dogs when they are not profitable. If profitable, do not invest, but make the best out of its current value. This may even mean selling the division's operations.

B) GE Nine-cell matrix

This matrix was developed in 1970s by the General Electric Company with the assistance of the consulting firm, McKinsey & Co, USA. This is also called GE multifactor portfolio matrix.

The GE matrix has been developed to overcome the obvious limitations of BCG matrix. This matrix consists of nine cells (3X3) based on two key variables:

- i) business strength
- ii) industry attractiveness

The horizontal axis represents business strength and the vertical axis represent industry attractiveness

The business strength is measured by considering such factors as:

- relative market share profit margins
- ability to compete on price and quality knowledge of customer and market
- competitive strengths and weaknesses technological capacity
- caliber of management

Industry attractiveness is measured considering such factors as :

- market size and growth rate industry profit margin competitive intensity economies of scale technology

social, environmental, legal and human aspects

The industry product-lines or business units are plotted as circles. The area of each circle is proportionate to industry sales. The pie within the circles represents the market share of the product line or business unit.

The nine cells of the GE matrix represent various degrees of industry attractiveness (high, medium or low) and business strength (strong, average and weak). After plotting each product line or business unit on the nine cell matrix, strategic choices are made depending on their position in the matrix.

Spotlight Strategy

GE matrix is also called “Stoplight” strategy matrix because the three zones are like green, yellow and red of traffic lights.

- 1) Green indicates invest/expand – if the product falls in green zone, the business strength is strong and industry is at least medium in attractiveness, the strategic decision should be to expand, to invest and to grow.
- 2) Yellow indicates select/earn – if the product falls in yellow zone, the business strength is low but industry attractiveness is high, it needs caution and managerial discretion for making the strategic choice
- 3) Red indicates harvest/divest – if the product falls in the red zone, the business strength is average or weak and attractiveness is also low or medium, the appropriate strategy should be divestment.

Advantages –

- 1) It used 9 cells instead of 4 cells of BCG
- 2) It considers many variables and does not lead to simplistic conclusions
- 3) High/medium/low and strong/average/low classification enables a finer distinction among business portfolio
- 4) It uses multiple factors to assess industry attractiveness and business strength, which allow users to select criteria appropriate to their situation

Limitations –

- 1) It can get quite complicated and cumbersome with the increase in businesses
- 2) Though industry attractiveness and business strength appear to be objective, they are in reality subjective judgements that may vary from one person to another
- 3) It cannot effectively depict the position of new business units in developing industry
- 4) It only provides broad strategic prescriptions rather than specifics of business policy

Difference between BCG and GE matrices –

BCG Matrix	GE Matrix
1. BCG matrix consists of four cells	1. GE matrix consists of nine cells
2. The business unit is rated against relative market share and industry growth rate	2. The business unit is rated against business strength and industry attractiveness

3. The matrix uses single measure to assess growth and market share	3. The matrix used multiple measures to assess business strength and industry attractiveness
4. The matrix uses two types of classification i.e high and low	4. The matrix uses three types of classification i.e high/medium/low and strong/average/weak
5. Has many limitations	5. Overcomes many limitations of BCG and is an improvement over it

SWOT ANALYSIS

A scan of the internal and external environment is an important part of the strategic planning process. Environmental factors internal to the firm usually can be classified as strengths (S) or weaknesses (W), and those external to the firm can be classified as opportunities (O) or threats (T). Such an analysis of the strategic environment is referred to as a **SWOT analysis**.

The SWOT analysis provides information that is helpful in matching the firm's resources and capabilities to the competitive environment in which it operates. As such, it is instrumental in strategy formulation and selection. The following diagram shows how a SWOT analysis fits into an environmental scan:

Strengths

A firm's strengths are its resources and capabilities that can be used as a basis for developing a [competitive advantage](#). Examples of such strengths include:

- patents
- strong brand names
- good reputation among customers
- cost advantages from proprietary know-how exclusive access to high grade natural resources favorable access to distribution networks

Weaknesses

The absence of certain strengths may be viewed as a weakness. For example, each of the following may be considered weaknesses:

- lack of patent protection a weak brand name
- poor reputation among customers high cost structure

- lack of access to the best natural resources lack of access to key distribution channels
- In some cases, a weakness may be the flip side of a strength. Take the case in which a firm has a large amount of manufacturing capacity. While this capacity may be considered a strength that competitors do not share, it also may be considered a weakness if the large investment in manufacturing capacity prevents the firm from reacting quickly to changes in the strategic environment.

Opportunities

The external environmental analysis may reveal certain new opportunities for profit and growth. Some examples of such opportunities include:

- an unfulfilled customer need
- arrival of new technologies loosening of regulations
- removal of international trade barriers

Threats

Changes in the external environmental also may present threats to the firm. Some examples of such threats include:

shifts in consumer tastes away from the firm's products
 emergence of substitute products new regulations
 increased trade barriers

Strategic Alternatives

Strategy

- A strategy is a unified, comprehensive, and integrated plan that relates the strategic advantages of the firm to the challenges of the environment. It is designed to ensure that the basic objective of the enterprise are achieved through proper execution by the organization

Levels of Strategies

Business level

Corporate Level Strategic Alternatives

Corporate level strategy

☀ Digitalization

Stability Strategies

Stability Strategies

A firm pursues stability strategy when

2. It continues to serve the public in the same product or service, market, and function sectors as defined in its business definition.
3. Its main strategic decisions focus on incremental improvement of functional performance.

Why Stability Strategies?

- ✿ It is less risky, involves less changes and people feel comfortable with things as they are
- ✿ The environment faced is relatively stable
- ✿ Expansion may be perceived as being threatening
- ✿ Consolidation is sought through stabilizing after a period of rapid expansion

Types of Stability Strategies

- ✿ No change strategies
- ✿ Pause/proceed with caution strategies
- ✿ Profit strategies

No Change Strategies

- ✿ Taking no decision sometimes, is a decision too!
- ✿ This strategy is relevant in predictable and certain external environment and stable organizational environment.
- ✿ Small and medium sized firms rely on this strategy

Profit Strategies

- ☀ Things do change
- ☀ It is assumed that the problem is short lived
- ☀ Only motive is sustaining profitability for a temporary phase
- ☀ It works only if the problems are really short lived

Pause/Proceed With Caution Strategies

- ✿ It is employed to test the ground before moving ahead with a full-fledged corporate strategy
- ✿ The purpose is to let the system adapt to the new strategies
- ✿ It is deliberate and conscious attempt

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Expansion Strategies

Expansion Strategies

- Concentration strategies
- Integration strategies
- Diversification strategies
- Cooperation strategies
- Internationalization strategies
- Digitalization strategies

Expansion Strategies

The corporate strategy of expansion is followed when an organization aims at high growth by substantially broadening the scope of one or more of its business in terms of their respective customer groups, customer functions and alternative technologies- singly or jointly-in order to improve its overall performance.

Expansion Strategies

- ✿ It may become imperative when the environment demands increase in pace of activity.
- ✿ Increasing size may lead to more control over the market vis-à-vis competitors.
- ✿ Advantage from the experience curve and scale of operation may accrue.

Expansion Strategies

- ✿ Expansion through concentration
- ✿ Expansion through integration
- ✿ Expansion through diversification
- ✿ Expansion through cooperation
- ✿ Expansion through internationalisation
- ✿ Expansion through digitation

Expansion Through Concentration

Concentration Strategies

- ✿ Concentration is a simple, first-level type of expansion strategy. It involves converging resources in one or more of a firm businesses in terms of their respective customer needs, customer functions, or alternative technologies-either singly or jointly- in such a manner that expansion results.

Concentration Strategies

- Concentration strategies involve an investment of resources in a product line for an identified market, with the help of proven technology.

Ansoff Product-Market Matrix

Product Market	Present	New
Present	Market Penetration	Product Development
New	Market Development	Diversification

Three Types of Concentration Strategies

- ✿ Market penetration
- ✿ Market development
- ✿ Product development
- ✿ Diversification

Market Penetration

Market penetration involves selling more product to the same market: a firm may attempt at focusing intensely on existing markets with its present products, using a market penetration type of concentration.

Market Development

It involves selling the same products to new markets: it may try attracting new users for existing products, resulting in a market development type of concentration.

Product Development

It involves selling new products to the same markets: it may introduce newer products in the existing markets by concentration on product development.

Expansion Through Integration

Integration Strategies

- ✿ Integration (from the Latin integer, meaning whole or entire) generally means combining parts so that they work together or form a whole. Informational technology , there are several common usages.
- ✿ Integration during product development process in which separately produced components or sub systems are combined and problems in their interactions are addressed.

Horizontal Integration

When an organisation takes up the same type of products at the same level of production or marketing process, it is said to follow a strategy of horizontal integration.

Vertical Integration

- When an organization starts making new products that serve its own needs, vertical integration takes place.
- Any new activity undertaken with the purpose of either supplying inputs (such as raw materials) or serving as a customer for outputs (such as marketing of firm's product) is vertical integration.

Expansion Through Diversification

Diversification Strategies

- When new products are made for new markets then diversification take place. The notion of diversifying is therefore related to the newness of products or markets or both.
- By adopting diversification, an organisation does something novel in terms of making new products or serving new markets or doing both simultaneously.

Concentric Diversification

- If the new business is in any way related to the original business in terms of the customer groups served, customer functions performed or alternative technologies employed, then it is concentric diversification.

Types of Concentric Diversification

- **Marketing-related concentric diversification-**: A similar type of product is offered with the help of unrelated technology.
- **Technology-related concentric diversification-**: A new type of product or service is provided with the help of related technology.
- **Marketing-and technology-related concentric diversification-**: A similar type of product or service is provided with the help of a related technology.

Conglomerate Diversification

- When an organisation adopts a strategy which requires taking up those activities which are unrelated to the existing business definition of any of its businesses, it is conglomerate diversification.

Why are Diversification Strategies adopted?

- Diversification strategies are adopted to minimize risk by spreading it over several business.
- Diversification may be used to capabilities and business model so as to maximize organizational strength or minimize weakness.
- Diversification may be the only way out if growth in existing business is blocked due to environmental and regulatory factors.

Expansion Through Internationalization

Internationalization Strategies

International strategies are type of expansion strategies that require organizations to market their products or services beyond the domestic or national market. For doing so, an organization would have to assess the international environment, evaluate its own capabilities and devise strategies to enter foreign markets.

Types Of Internationalization Strategies

- **International strategy-:**

Firms adopt an international strategy when they create value by transferring products and services to foreign markets where these products and services are not available.

- **Multidomestic strategy-:**

Firms adopt a multidomestic strategy when they try to achieve a high level of local responsiveness by matching their products and service offerings to the national conditions operating in the countries they operate in.

Types of Internationalization strategies

- **Global strategy-:**

Firms adopt a global strategy when they rely on a low-cost approach based on reaping the benefits of experience-curve effects and location economies and offering standardised products and services across different countries.

- **Transnational strategy-:**

Firms adopt a transnational strategy when they adopt a combined approach of low-cost and high local responsiveness simultaneously, for their products and services.

Advantages Of Expansion Through Internationalisation

- **Realising economies scale-**: By expanding sales volume through international expansion, firms can realise cost economies of scale.
- **Realising economies of scope-**: Firms develop valuable competencies and skills when they operate in home markets and implement particular business models.

Advantages Of Expansion Through Internationalisation

- **Expansion and extension of markets-:** Economies of scale and scope enable firms to expand their markets from local to global markets, in a two-way beneficial relationship where the expanded markets enable the firms to realise lower costs and attain economies of scale.
- **Access to resources overseas-:** by expanding internationally, firms gain access to resources overseas that they do not get when they operate in domestic markets only.

Disadvantages Of Expansion Through Internationalisation

- **Higher risks-:** International expansion often entails a higher risk as compared to a situation where a firm operate only domestically.
- **Difficulty in managing cultural diversity-:** International firms face challenges of managing cultural diversity within and outside.

Disadvantages Of Expansion Through Internationalization

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Disadvantages Of Expansion Through Internationalisation

- **High bureaucratic costs-**: Operating internationally require an extensive coordination between the home office and the foreign operations and subsidiaries.
- **Trade barriers-**: Despite liberalisation of trade between countries, substantial trade barriers in the form of tariffs, pricing restrictions, differing standards or local content requirements exist.

Expansion Through Cooperative Strategies

Cooperative Strategies

- Corporate strategy is basically the growth design of the firm: it spells out the growth objective of the firm-the direction, extent, pace and timing of the firm's growth.
- Corporate strategy is basically concerned with the choice of businesses, product and markets.

Scope Of Corporate Strategy

- It can also be viewed as the objective-strategy design of the firm.
- It is the design for filling the firm's strategic planning gap.
- It is concerned with the choice of the firm's products and markets.
- It ensure that the right fit is achieved between the firm and its environment.
- It helps built the relevant competitive advantages for the firm.

Types Of Corporate Strategies

- Mergers and acquisitions
- Joint Ventures
- Strategic Alliances

Merger and Acquisition

- **Mergers and acquisitions** -: refers to the aspect of corporate strategy, corporate finance and management dealing with the buying, selling, dividing and combining of different companies and similar entities that can help an enterprise grow rapidly in its sector or location of origin, or a new field or new location, without creating a subsidiary, other child entity or using a joint venture.

Types of Mergers and Acquisitions

- Horizontal mergers
- Vertical mergers
- Concentric mergers
- Conglomerate mergers

Reasons for Mergers and Acquisitions

- To increase the value of the organizations stock.
- To increase the growth rate and make a good investment.
- To reduce competition.
- To improve the stability of its earnings and sales.
- To avail tax concessions and benefits.

How Mergers and Acquisitions take place?

- Spell out the objective.
- Assess managerial quality.
- Indicate how the objective would be achieved.
- Check the compatibility of business styles.
- Treat people with dignity and concern.

Joint venture strategies

- A joint venture could be considered as an entity resulting from a long-term contractual agreement between two or more parties, to undertake mutually beneficial economic activities, exercise joint control and contribute equity and share in the profit or losses of the entity.

Conditions for joint ventures

- When an activity is uneconomical for an organization to do alone.
- When the risk of business has to be shared and, therefore, is reduced for the participating firms.
- When the distinctive competence of two or more organisations can be brought together.

Types of joint venture

- Between two Indian organisations in one industry.
- Between two Indian organisations across different industries.
- Between an Indian organisation and a foreign organisation in India.
- Between an Indian organisation and a foreign organisation in that foreign country.
- Between an Indian organisation and a foreign organisation in a third country.

Benefits in joint venture

- Minimizing risk
- Reducing an individual company's investment
- Creating access to foreign technology
- Broad-based equity participation
- Access to government and political support and entering new fields of business and synergistic advantages

Disadvantages in joint ventures

- Problems in equity participation
- Foreign exchange regulations
- Lack of proper coordination among participating firms
- Cultural and behavioural differences and the possibility of conflict among the partners

Strategic Alliances

- Yoshino and Rangan define strategic alliances in terms of three necessary and sufficient characteristics:
- Two or more firms unite to pursue a set of agreed upon goals, but remain independent subsequent to the information of the alliances
- The partners firms contribute on a continuing basis, in one or more key strategic area, for ex. technology

Reasons For Strategic Alliances

- Entering new markets
- Reducing manufacturing costs
- Developing and diffusing technology

Types Of Strategic Alliances

- Procompetitive alliances (low interaction/low conflict).
- Noncompetitive alliances (high interaction/low conflict).
- Competitive alliance (high interaction/high conflict).
- Precompetitive alliance (low interaction/high conflict).

Managing Strategic Alliances

- Clearly define a strategy and assign responsibilities.
- Phase in the relationship between the partners.
- Blend the culture of the partners
- Provide for an exist strategy

Pitfalls In Strategic Alliances

- Lack of trust and commitment
- Perceived misunderstandings among partners
- Conflicting goals and interests
- Inadequate preparation for entering into partnership
- Hasty implementation of plans and focussing on controlling the relationship rather than on managing it for mutual benefits

Digitalization Strategies

- Digitalisation is defined as digital coding of information and the growing productivity gains in processing and transmission it enable.

The versatility and economy of digitalisation makes information available efficiently, widely and cheaply within outside organisations.

Principles Underpinning Digitalisation Strategies

- Outsourcing to the customer by letting them perform many of the service functions on their own
- Cannibalizing their markets before their competitors do it
- Treating each customer as a market segment through mass customisation
- Structuring every transaction as a joint venture with the customer

Principles Underpinning Digitalisation Strategies

- Managing innovation as a portfolio of options so that risk is minimised
- Destroying one's value chain
- Replacing rude (human) interfaces with learning interfaces through customer-operated facilities

Digitisation, Value Chain and Value System

- Value chains and value systems have worked in well-understood ways, where input the form of raw materials provided through inbound logistics to the organisation where value- addition takes place through operations . The finished products are then supplied through marketing and sales to the customer. After- sales services support the value chain process wherever needed.

Digitalisation transforms the value chain and value system in several different ways

- Deconstruction- Digitalization changes the way that value chains and value systems might work.
- Disintermediation- when some process in the value chain are eliminated
- Re-intermediation- When processes in the value chain are supplemented by one or more intermediaries.

Digitalization transforms the value chain and value system in several different ways

- Industry morphing-Digitalisation has created a situation where traditional industries are transforming into entirely new types of industries.
- Cannibalisation-A set of activities performed in the value chain are being replaced by a new set of activities, thus eating away that part of value chain

Digitalization transforms the value chain and value system in several different ways

- Techno-intensification- Digitalisation of the value chain and value system results in a situation where there is more intensive use of technology and a decreased use of human resources.
- Re-channelling

Retrenchment Strategies

Retrenchment strategies

A retrenchment strategy is pursued by a firm when:

- ✿ It sees the desirability of or necessity for reducing its product or service lines, markets, or functions
- ✿ It focuses its strategic decisions on functional improvement through the reduction of activities in units with negative cash flows.

Why Retrenchment strategies?

- ✿ The management no longer wishes to remain in business either partly or wholly, due to continuous losses and the organization becoming viable
- ✿ Stability can be ensured by reallocation of resources from unprofitable to profitable businesses
- ✿ The environment faced is threatening

Types of Retrenchment strategies

✿ Turnaround strategies

✿ Divestment strategies

✿ Liquidation strategies

Combination Strategies

Combination Strategies

Combination strategies are used by a firm when:

- ✿ Its main strategic decisions focus on the conscious use of several grand strategies (expansion, stability, retrenchment) at the same time(simultaneously) in several SBUs of the company.

Combination Strategies

- ✿ It plans to use several grand strategies at different future times (sequentially)

Why Combination Strategies?

- ✿ If the organization is large and faces complex environment
- ✿ The organization is composed of different businesses, each of which lies in a different industry, requiring a different response

Combination Strategies

- Simultaneous combination strategies
- Sequential combination strategies
- Combination of simultaneous and sequential strategies

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